

Nuclear effective interactions in the inner crust of a neutron star

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The nuclear effective interactions in the inner crust are investigated in detail where the energy density functional (EDF) is constructed with the help of the Hartree-Fock and the Extended Thomas Fermi approximations (ETF) to treat the nucleons inside and outside the clusters. Considering the destabilization of the crystal lattice, the second order perturbation to the energy density functional is explicitly formalized. Furthermore, we work the density profiles and other bizarre features of the non-spherical nuclei and the pasta phases at the crust-core boundary. Analysing the smooth composition model of the ground state, we also discuss the effects of these defects on vortex pinning.

I. NUCLEAR EFFECTIVE INTERACTIONS IN THE INNER CRUST

In the inner crust of neutron stars, matter at sub-nuclear densities, i.e. $\rho > 4.3 \times 10^{11} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, is frequently composed of nuclei which may coexist with a sea of neutrons. So, what we have is the neutron-rich atomic nuclei coexisting with a neutron fluid in addition to the background of electrons which ensures electrical neutrality. The contributions to the effective interaction between nuclei due to the presence of the neutrons outside nuclei, in addition to the screened Coulomb interaction must be considered [1][2]. These interactions could alter the equilibrium lattice structure since they affect the collective modes of the crust. Specifically, the neutrons give rise to an attractive interaction between nuclei which makes the lattice unstable. This attraction can destabilize the matter at finite wavelengths when the Coulomb interactions are reduced.

Near the the bottom of the crust, the shape of the nuclei may change from roughly spherical to cylindrical or plane-parallel due to the competition between nuclear attraction and Coulomb repulsion which rearrange the neutrons and protons from many nuclei into complex non-spherical shapes such as flat plates (lasagna) or thin rods (spaghetti) [3]. This is called the *nuclear pasta* phase which is the final phase just before the nuclei's disintegration to the core (see the illustration Figure 1). The analytic descriptions of the neutron and proton local density profiles for the ground-state matter throughout the outer and inner neutron star crusts will be investigated in § II.

To study the highly neutron-rich nuclei one needs to develop a universal nuclear energy functional that can be applied to stable, neutron rich, and very heavy nuclei, and to neutron rich matter in astrophysics including neutron stars. Even the recent nuclear physics experiments cannot probe all the physical conditions covered inside a neutron star; therefore, theoretical models are required to extrapolate to unknown regions of the nuclear chart. The nuclear energy-density functional (EDF) theory has become an approved way of treating the medium-mass and heavy nuclei. It is also suitable for investigating the different regions inside a neutron star. Semi-classical models can be effective to approach the nucleons inside and outside clusters. These models are good approximations to the full Hartree-Fock equations (see § IA). The total energy is written as a functional of the density of each species and their gradients [4][p. 92]. Then, it is possible to obtain the nuclear functional using the extended Thomas-Fermi (ETF) approach [5] (see § IB).

A. Hartree-Fock calculations with nucleon-nucleon interaction

The quantum mechanical formulation of the many body problem is based on the generalization of the Schrödinger equation formulation of the one and two-body problems. To study the inner crust, let us consider the matter divided into unit cells [6].

The effective Hamiltonian for $A = Z + N$ nucleon is

$$H_N^{\text{eff}} = \sum_{j=1}^A \bar{T}_j + \sum_{k < j \leq A} \bar{v}_{jk}^{\text{eff}} \quad (1)$$

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FIG. 1. The illustration of the effective interactions in the inner crust. Nuclear pasta configurations retrieved from Caplan and Horowitz [3].

where $\bar{T}_j = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_j} + \sum_{j=1}^A V_j^{\text{eff}}$ is the kinetic energy term containing the effective potential, while $\bar{v}_{jk}^{\text{eff}}$ is the interaction term between jk nucleon pair. The basic short range Skyrme-type interaction is embedded in the second term [7]. The complete Hamiltonian of the unit cell is given as

$$H_{\text{cell}}^{\text{eff}} = H_N^{\text{eff}} + V_{\text{Coul}} + H_e \quad (2)$$

where V_{Coul} is the Coulomb interaction between electrons and protons, and H_e describes the uniform electron gas. The Hartree-Fock approximation for the many body wave function is formed from single particle wave functions using the Slater determinants

$$\Phi_{NZ} = F_{NZ} \det \left[\psi_{\alpha_i}^{(p)}(\vec{r}_k, s_k) \right] \det \left[\psi_{\beta_j}^{(n)}(\vec{r}_l, s_l) \right] \quad (3)$$

where $\psi_{\alpha_i}^{(p)}$, $\psi_{\beta_j}^{(n)}$ are square-integrable single particle wave functions for $(j, l = 1, \dots, N)$ and $(i, k = 1, \dots, Z)$, and F_{NZ} is a normalization constant. The spin and space coordinates are given for k -th proton and l -th neutron. The set of quantum numbers of states are given as (α_i, β_j) .

Negele and Vautherin [8] used spherical symmetry to approximate the nuclei arranged in a bcc lattice, which minimizes the Coulomb lattice energy. The Wigner-Seitz cell is introduced to simplify the energy of a unit cell, which is a sphere with the same volume as the unit cell in the bcc lattice [9]. The radius of the Wigner-Seitz cell, R_c and the lattice constant a is related to the cell volume V_c and the number density of nuclei n_N as $a^3 = 4\pi R_c^3/3 = 1/n_N$, where the number density of uniform electron gas is $n_e = Z/V_c$. So, using the variational principle, the Hartree-Fock equations for $\psi_{\alpha_i}^{(p)}$ and $\psi_{\beta_j}^{(n)}$ can be derived by minimizing the energy functional

$$E_{\text{cell}} \left[\psi_{\alpha_i}^{(p)}, \psi_{\beta_j}^{(n)} \right] = \langle \Phi_{NZ} \Phi_e | H_{\text{cell}}^{\text{eff}} | \Phi_{NZ} \Phi_e \rangle, \quad (4)$$

at fixed cell volume V_c , where Φ_e is the plane wave-function for the free electron gas. The complete wave function will be the multiplication of the individual wave functions, i.e. $\Phi_{NZ} \Phi_e$. The boundary condition for $r = R_c$ is arbitrary and can be worrisome when nuclear radius is comparable to the cell radius (see comments on [10]). Overall these approaches search for the best independent-particle approximation for an interacting system of fermions. As we can see, one simply should form a many-body wave function of the atom as a Slater determinant using some one-particle states, then choose these so as to minimize the expectation value of the Hamiltonian in Equation 2.

B. Extended Thomas Fermi (ETF) calculations

In the neutron drip regime, the number of nucleons inside the unit cell rapidly grow. Large sizes of nuclei can simplify the Hartree-Fock approximations via semi-classical models in which the quantities are taken on the average. The minimization given in Equation 4 can be performed at fixed densities, $\bar{n}_n = N/V_c$ and $\bar{n}_p = Z/V_c$. In the ETF approximation, the total energy of a unit cell is

$$E_{cell} = \int_{cell} \{ \varepsilon_{cell}(r) + [m_n n_n(r) + m_p n_p(r)] c^2 \} d^3r. \quad (5)$$

As we can see, the radial nucleon density distributions are crucial for ETF calculations. The local density profiles of neutrons and protons within the nuclei are $n_n(r)$ and $n_p(r)$ respectively. Here r is the distance either from the center of a spherical nucleus, or from the symmetry axis of a cylindrical nuclei (§ A 1), or from the symmetry plane of a slab-like nucleus (§ A 2). The distributions inside a Wigner-Seitz cell can be written as

$$n_j(r) = \begin{cases} (n_j^{cent} - n_j^o) \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{R_j} \right)^{t_j} \right]^3 + n_j^o & \text{at } r < R_j, \\ n_j^o & \text{at } r \geq R_j, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where j can be proton or neutron and n_j^{cent} , n_j^o , t_j and R_j are the fit parameters. The value of t_j controls the sharpness of the density profile, and R_j is the size of the nucleus [11]. For the spherical profile, since all the protons are inside the nucleus ($n_p^o = 0$), we only need to determine n_n^o by using the following relation

$$\bar{A} = A + \frac{4\pi}{3} (R_c^3 - r_n^3) n_n^o = \frac{4\pi}{3} R_c^3 n_b, \quad (7)$$

where \bar{A} is the number of nucleons within a Wigner-Seitz cell. For the spherical nuclei, the number density of outside neutrons can be reduced to a simple relation

$$n_n^o = \frac{3}{4\pi} \left(\frac{V_c n_b - A}{R_c^3 - r_n^3} \right). \quad (8)$$

The density distributions of protons and neutrons inside the spherical cell is shown in Figure 2, the neutrons appear outside the nuclei when $r > R_j$. It is convenient that we get much more outside neutrons for a nuclei which have appreciably higher neutron excess (see Table II and Table III for the corresponding parameters).

C. Compressible liquid drop model (CLDM)

Throughout our work in [12], we have briefly mentioned the LDM model and constructed a modified version of the SEMF by decomposing the binding energy into several terms. Similarly, the compressible liquid drop model (CLDM) enables one to separate various terms in E_{cell} and identify their contribution. CLDM allows us to impose a condition of the compression of the nuclear matter within the nuclei by the pressure of the neutron gas. It is separated into the nuclear contribution E_{nuc} , Coulomb contribution E_{Coul} , and uniform electron Fermi gas contribution E_e as follows

$$E_{cell} = E_{nuc} + E_{Coul} + E_e. \quad (9)$$

In the CLDM, nucleons are distributed over three subsystem. The denser nucleons inside the nuclei, n_j^i , nuclear interface ($i-o$ interface) and far from the nuclear surface, n_j^o . These phases are in chemical and mechanical equilibrium. In general, to study the properties of the neutron star crust, one often uses the radius of the protons and neutrons (r_n, r_p). The equivalent radius r_j is defined as the radius of the imaginary step-like density distribution [10][p. 133]

$$r_j = \left[1 - 3 \frac{d+2}{d+2+t_j} \gamma_j^{t_j} + 3 \frac{d+2}{d+2+2t_j} \gamma_j^{2t_j} - \frac{d+2}{d+2+3t_j} \gamma_j^{3t_j} \right]^{1/2} \times \left[1 - \frac{3d}{d+t_j} \gamma_j^{t_j} + \frac{3d}{d+2t_j} \gamma_j^{2t_j} - \frac{d}{d+3t_j} \gamma_j^{3t_j} \right]^{-1/2} \gamma_j R_j, \quad (10)$$

where $\gamma_j = r_j^{\max}/R_j$ and $r_j^{\max} = \min(R_j, R_c)$. In most of the cases we will consider $\gamma_j \rightarrow 1$, unless r_j exceeds the Wigner-Seitz cell radius R_c which might happen at the crust-core boundary where $R_c = r_j$. In that case we

FIG. 2. Density distributions of protons and neutrons inside the spherical nuclei for the cases $Y_p = 0.5$ and $Y_p = 0.465$ where Y_p is the fraction of the protons.

get $\gamma_j < 1$. The corresponding models should satisfy the condition of $r_j < R_c$. For spherical nuclei the dimension parameter $d = 3$ ($d = 2 \rightarrow$ cylindrical nuclei, $d = 1 \rightarrow$ plane nuclei). We can also write the equivalent neutron and proton densities as follows

$$\begin{aligned} n_j^i &= n_j^o + \frac{d}{r_j^d} \int_0^{r_j^{\max}} (n(r) - n_j^o) r^{d-1} dr \\ &= n_j^o + \left[1 - \frac{3d}{d+t_j} \gamma_j^{t_j} + \frac{3d}{d+2t_j} \gamma_j^{2t_j} - \frac{d}{d+3t_j} \gamma_j^{3t_j} \right] \frac{R_j^d}{r_j^d} (n_j^{\text{cen}} - n_j^o). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

D. The energy density functional (EDF) formalism

Now, we have all the tools we need to formalize the total energy density of a unit cell in terms of the neutron and proton number densities, $n_n(r)$ and $n_p(r)$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{tot}} = \varepsilon_{\text{nuc}} + \varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_{\text{coul}} + (n_n m_n + n_p m_p + n_e m_e) c^2. \quad (12)$$

We will assume that the matter is electrically neutral and therefore electron density n_e is equal to proton density n_p . So, we get the following

$$\varepsilon_{\text{tot}} = \varepsilon_{\text{nuc}} + \varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_{\text{coul}} + (n_n m_n + n_p (m_p + m_e)) c^2. \quad (13)$$

The first term in Equation 12 includes Skyrme type interaction and it is given as

$$\varepsilon_{\text{nuc}} = \frac{3}{R_c^3} \int_0^{R_c} \varepsilon_{\text{SKY}}^{\text{ETF}}(r) d^3r, \quad (14)$$

where the Skyrme type interaction varies between several models. We will use the **GSk1** Skyrme model parameters [13][p. 68] (see Table I for the parameters).

$$\begin{aligned}
\varepsilon_{SKY}^{ETF}(r) = & \frac{3h^2}{40M\pi^2} \left(\frac{3\pi^2}{2}\right)^{2/3} n^{5/3} H_{5/3} + \frac{t_0}{8} n^2 (2(x_0 + 2) - (2x_0 + 1)H_2) \\
& + \frac{1}{48} (t_{31}n^{\sigma_1+2} (2(x_{31} + 2) - 2(2x_{31} + 1)H_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{48} (t_{32}n^{\sigma_2+2} (2(x_{32} + 2) - 2(2x_{32} + 1)H_2)) \\
& + \frac{1}{48} (t_{33}n^{\sigma_3+2} (2(x_{33} + 2) - 2(2x_{33} + 1)H_2)) \\
& + \frac{3}{40} \left(\frac{3\pi^2}{2}\right)^{2/3} n^{8/3} (aH_{5/3} + bH_{8/3}) \\
& + \frac{3}{40} \left(\frac{3\pi^2}{2}\right)^{2/3} n^{\delta+8/3} \left(t_4(x_4 + 2)H_{5/3} - t_4(x_4 + \frac{1}{2})H_{8/3}\right) \\
& + \frac{3}{40} \left(\frac{3\pi^2}{2}\right)^{2/3} n^{\gamma+8/3} \left(t_5(x_5 + 2)H_{5/3} - t_5(x_5 + \frac{1}{2})H_{8/3}\right),
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where $n = n_n(r) + n_p(r)$ is the local density, M is the free nucleon mass, and

$$H_n(y) = 2^{n-1} (y^n + (1-y)^n), \tag{16}$$

$$a = t_1(x_1 + 2) + t_2(x_2 + 1), \tag{17}$$

$$b = \frac{1}{2} (t_2(2x_2 + 1) - t_1(2x_1 + 1)), \tag{18}$$

$$y = Z/A. \tag{19}$$

The second term includes the kinetic energy of the electrons which can be derived from the particle energy

$$\varepsilon_e = \frac{4\pi}{5h^3 m_e} \left(\frac{3h^3}{8\pi}\right)^{5/3} n_e^{2/3}, \tag{20}$$

here $n_e = Z/V_e$ is the average electron density. The third term is the Coulomb interaction term between protons and electrons. It is usually decomposed into the classical part and the quantum correlated part which includes Pauli exclusion principle.

$$\varepsilon_{coul}^{class} = \frac{1}{2} e (n_p(r) - n_e) \Phi, \tag{21}$$

here Φ is the electrostatic potential obeying Poisson's equation

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = -4\pi (n_p(r) - n_e). \tag{22}$$

Considering the volume fraction occupied by the protons inside the nucleus (n_p^i) is $u = (r_p/R_c)^3$, the Coulomb contribution can be written as follows

$$\varepsilon_{coul} = \frac{4\pi}{5} (n_p^i)^2 e^2 r_p^2 f(u), \tag{23}$$

where the function [5][pp. 17-21] $f(u) = u - \frac{3}{2}u^{2/3} + \frac{u^2}{2}$.

The quantum correlated part is given by Slater-Kohn-Sham functional [14] for the inhomogeneous electron gas

$$\varepsilon_{coul}^{quant} = -\frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{3}{\pi}\right)^{1/3} e^2 \left(n_p^{4/3}(r) + n_e^{4/3}(r)\right). \tag{24}$$

Finally, we can construct the total energy density functional

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{tot} = & \frac{3}{R_c^3} \int_0^{R_c} \varepsilon_{SKY}^{ETF}(r) d^3r + \frac{4\pi}{5h^3m_e} \left(\frac{3h^3}{8\pi}\right)^{5/3} n_e^{2/3} \\ & + \frac{4\pi}{5} (n_p^i)^2 e^2 r_p^2 f(u) - \frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{3}{\pi}\right)^{1/3} e^2 [n_p^{4/3}(r) + n_e^{4/3}(r)] \\ & + [n_n(r)m_n + n_p(r)(m_p + m_e)] c^2. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

E. Destabilization of the crystal lattice

The neutrons give rise to an attractive interaction between nuclei which can destabilize the matter at finite wavelengths when the Coulomb interactions are reduced. In this section, we will consider the second order perturbation to the energy density functional which is obtained in § ID. In many-body calculations the effective interaction between particles is expressed as the sum of two terms, a direct interaction term, which represents the energy change when the average particle density is held fixed, and an induced interaction term, which results from changes in the average density for a binary mixture consisting of neutrons and protons [15] [1], [16][p. 15]. The second order change can be written in the Hurwitz matrix form

$$\delta^2\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2} \bar{r}^T \mathbf{H} \bar{r}, \quad (26)$$

where \bar{r} is the column vector representing the deviation in number densities, i.e. δn_j and each term can be written explicitly as follows

$$\delta^2\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} n_n(r) - n_n(r^*) & n_p(r) - n_p(r^*) \end{bmatrix}}_{\bar{r}^T} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{pp} & \varepsilon_{np} \\ \varepsilon_{pn} & \varepsilon_{nn} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{H}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} n_n(r) - n_n(r^*) \\ n_p(r) - n_p(r^*) \end{bmatrix}}_{\bar{r}},$$

where $\varepsilon_{ij} = \partial^2\varepsilon/\partial n_i\partial n_j$, $\varepsilon(n_p, n_n)$ being the energy density of the system [17]. For electrically neutral matter the background electron density n_e is equal to the proton density and is therefore not an independent variable. The condition for the system to be stable to small density inhomogeneities is positive definiteness of the principal minors of \mathbf{H} ,

$$\varepsilon_{nn} > 0, \quad \varepsilon_{pp} > 0, \quad (27)$$

The matrix \mathbf{H} is symmetric, so $\varepsilon_{np} = \varepsilon_{pn}$ and we also have the inequality

$$\varepsilon_{pp} - \frac{\varepsilon_{np}^2}{\varepsilon_{nn}} > 0, \quad (28)$$

where ε_{pp} is the direct interaction term and it represents the change in the energy when n_p is changed, keeping n_n fixed or we can equally say that it is the energy required to add a second proton to the neutron fluid. The second term $-\varepsilon_{np}^2/\varepsilon_{nn}$ is the induced interaction term and represents the reduction of the energy due to changes in n_n .

Since we have already obtained the energy density functional as a function of the distance from the center of the Wigner-Seitz cell, the partial derivatives can be calculated using the chain rule

$$\mu_n = \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{tot}}{\partial n_n} = \frac{d\varepsilon_{tot}}{dr} \left(\frac{dn_n}{dr} \right)^{-1}, \quad \delta n_p = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\varepsilon_{nn} = \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_{tot}}{\partial n_n^2} = \frac{d^2 \varepsilon_{tot}}{dr^2} \left(\frac{dn_n}{dr} \right)^{-2} \quad (30)$$

$$\mu_p = \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{tot}}{\partial n_p} = \frac{d\varepsilon_{tot}}{dr} \left(\frac{dn_p}{dr} \right)^{-1}, \quad \delta n_n = 0 \quad (31)$$

$$\varepsilon_{pp} = \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_{tot}}{\partial n_p^2} = \frac{d^2 \varepsilon_{tot}}{dr^2} \left(\frac{dn_p}{dr} \right)^{-2} \quad (32)$$

$$\varepsilon_{np} = \varepsilon_{pn} = \frac{d\mu_p}{dr} \left(\frac{dn_n}{dr} \right)^{-1}, \quad \delta n_p = 0 \quad (33)$$

where μ_i is the chemical potential of the species i , i.e. the change in the energy density for a unit change in the number density. The Coulomb effects are also important since the electron density is changed when proton density is altered. This contributes to the direct interaction term ε_{pp}

$$\begin{aligned} (\varepsilon_{pp})_e &= \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_e}{\partial n_e^2} \\ &\approx \frac{1}{3} \frac{\mu_e}{n_e} \approx \frac{1}{3} \frac{\hbar k_e c}{n_e}, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where $k_e = (3\pi^2 n_e)^{1/3}$ is the electron Fermi wave number. Furthermore, the Coulomb energy of the lattice of nuclei changes. For a spherical unit cell we have

$$\varepsilon^{lattice} = -\frac{9}{10} n_e \frac{Z^{2/3} e^2}{r_e}, \quad (35)$$

where r_e is the classical electron radius. Thus, the ratio of the lattice and electronic contributions to the direct interaction term is given by

$$\frac{\varepsilon^{lattice}}{\varepsilon_{pp}^e} \approx -0.05337 \left(\frac{Z}{40} \right)^{2/3}. \quad (36)$$

To estimate the contributions of the nuclear interactions to the thermodynamic derivatives, these Coulomb interactions must be removed from the ε_{pp} , so we get

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{pp}^{nuc} &= \varepsilon_{pp} - \varepsilon_{pp}^e \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon^{lattice}}{\varepsilon_{pp}^e} \right), \\ &= \varepsilon_{pp} - (\varepsilon_{pp}^e + \varepsilon^{lattice}). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

If we define a quantity such as

$$\Gamma = \frac{\varepsilon_{np}^2}{\varepsilon_{pp}^{nuc} \varepsilon_{nn}}, \quad (38)$$

we can compare the ε_{pp}^{nuc} with the magnitude of the induced interaction without the removal of the Coulomb interactions. If the direct and induced interactions are canceled, this ratio would be unity. As it is given in the stability relations, the configuration would be stable if the principal minors of the matrix \mathbf{H} are positive. We can summarize the situation here ;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } \Gamma < 1 & \quad \det[\mathbf{H}] > 0, \text{ stable lattice} \\ \text{for } \Gamma = 1 & \quad \det[\mathbf{H}] = 0, \\ \text{for } \Gamma > 1 & \quad \det[\mathbf{H}] < 0, \text{ unstable lattice.} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

II. SMOOTH COMPOSITION MODEL (SCM) OF THE GROUND STATE

In § IB, the nucleon distributions inside the Wigner-Seitz cell are investigated for a spherical nuclei using ETF calculations. Since our main goal is to understand the physics when the nuclei coexist with the neutron and electron clusters, we will only investigate the nuclei in the inner crust and omit the low density regions in the outer crust where $10^8 \text{ g cm}^{-3} \leq \rho \leq \rho_{\text{drip}}$. The analytic description of the neutron and proton local density profiles for the ground-state matter including non-spherical phases of atomic nuclei is referred as the *smooth composition model* (SCM).

A. Nuclei in the inner crust and the pasta phases

1. Spherical profile - gnocchi phase

The fit parameters for spherical nuclei at the ground-state matter at the mean baryon number density $n_b = 0.03 \text{ fm}^{-3}$ ($\rho = 4.98 \times 10^{13} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) is given in Table II. The density distributions are calculated with the help of Equation 6 (see section A).

Similarly n_j^i , n_j^o and n_j^{cent} are calculated for $Y_p = 0.465$ by using the Equation 11 and Equation 10 and are presented in Table III. The density profile for the spherical nuclei is shown in Figure 2.

2. Exotic nuclei

Under compression, the ions in the crust rearrange into exotic shapes in order to minimize their energy. The competition between the nuclear attraction of protons and neutrons and the Coulomb repulsion of the protons creates a variety of non-spherical and so called “inside-out” shapes (with voids replacing particles) [3] (see Figure 1). Proceeding with the results obtained by Oyamatsu [11], the phase with spherical nuclei in the inner crust is followed by the phase with rod-like cylindrical nuclei (**spaghetti**) up to $n_b \approx 0.07 \text{ fm}^{-3}$ ($\rho \approx 1.2 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) and the phase with slab-like plane-parallel nuclei (**lasagna**) up to $n_b \approx 0.08 \text{ fm}^{-3}$ ($\rho \approx 1.37 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$). Then, we have two phases where the roles of the nuclear matter and neutron matter are reversed. The inverse cylindrical nuclei (**antispaghetti**) appear when $n_b \approx 0.85 \text{ fm}^{-3}$ ($\rho \approx 1.42 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) and the “Swiss cheese” inverted-spheres (**antignocchi**) appear when $n_b \approx 0.86 \text{ fm}^{-3}$ ($\rho \approx 1.43 \times 10^{14} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$).

To be able to grasp the physics of the phase transitions of the nuclei, one can also consider the thermodynamic formulation that provides useful insights into the properties of the neutron skin, i.e. $r_n - r_p$. The skin may be regarded as being the result of adsorption of neutrons at the surface [18][p. 456]. If the surface tension decreases, the tendency of the neutrons being at the interface increases. For a neutron-rich nuclei, it is expected to have a neutron skin rather than the proton skin. Similarly, for the ordinary, spherical nuclei it is intuitive to expect larger neutron radius relative to the proton radius. With increasing baryon density, deficit of neutrons appear for the spaghetti and lasagna phases. Conversely, as it is shown in Figure 5 the anti-structures, i.e. antignocchi and antispaghetti phases, have larger proton radii. The protons appear outside the nuclei i.e. we get an appreciable proton deficit. That is one of the main reasons of getting negative results for the inside protons for the anti-phases of the nuclei (see Table III).

These profiles of the exotic nuclei can be useful for the topological characterization of neutron star crusts. In general, lasagnas and spaghettis have positive curvatures, gnocchis have positive curvatures and all anti-structures reverse the curvature (see [19]).

FIG. 3. Density profiles of protons and neutrons for gnocchi, spaghetti, and lasagna phases of the matter.

FIG. 4. Density profiles of protons and neutrons for different phases of the matter. In the antispaghetti and antignocchi phases with the roles of nuclear matter and neutron matter reversed, the local number density of neutrons and protons increases with increasing distance r from the center of the Wigner-Seitz cell.

FIG. 5. Density profiles of protons and neutrons including n_j^i , n_j^o phases.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Remarks on the nuclear effective interactions in the inner crust

In § I, the energy density functional (EDF) is constructed with the help of the Hartree-Fock and the Extended Thomas Fermi approximations (ETF) to treat the nucleons inside and outside clusters. In § IE, we have supported the idea of the asymmetric nuclei by considering the destabilization of the crystal lattice with the nuclear effective interactions in the inner crust. The outside neutrons gave rise to an attractive interaction between nuclei which destabilized the matter at finite wavelengths. Recent results of Kobyakov and Pethick [1] suggests that $\Gamma = \varepsilon_{np}^2 / \varepsilon_{pp}^{nuc} \varepsilon_{nn} > 1$ which corresponds to the destabilization of the crystal when the Coulomb interactions are reduced properly.

B. Remarks on the non-spherical nuclei and the pasta phases

In § II, the bizarre features of the density profiles of the pasta phases are investigated. Our work was mainly focused on the local behaviors of these phases which constitute the small fraction of a neutron star, though, some of the global properties of the crust can also be inferred. The effect of nonspherical nuclei on pulsar glitches and cooling of neutron stars is particularly interesting. Pulsar glitches are usually considered to be manifestations of a sudden release of neutron superfluid vortices trapped by some pinning centers in the crust. The force required to pin vortices might result from the pasta phases, impurities and the defects in lattice [20]. Furthermore, the superfluid vortices might be trapped inside the bubble structures for a reasonable amount of time in which the forces exerted on the bubbles result in the deformation of the bubbles. The interaction between the surfaces of the bubbles and the superfluid cause a sudden shock wave or liquid jet bursts which may eventually release the vortices. In particular, cage-like structures formed by the interaction of spherical bubble structures with their surrounding neighbors can trap the superfluid. These trapping times can be calculated and compared with observational glitch data. A suitable analogy for the surface where this interaction takes place can be drawn from nature; the minimal surface formed by soap bubbles when they interact with each other and with an external fluid, and the resulting jet shock that occurs as a result of this interaction. However, this theory would require careful computation of the pinning energy for such bubble structures.

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Appendix A: Spherical profile - gnocchi phase

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_p(r) &= 2.7774 \times 10^{-2} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{9.3707} \right)^{6.2741} \right]^3, \\
 n_n(r) &= 7.5384 \times 10^{-2} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{11.667} \right)^{4.6250} \right]^3 + 5.2738 \times 10^{-4}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{A1}$$

1. Rod-like nuclei - spaghetti phase

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_p(r) &= 0.09525 \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{9.78} \right)^{3.2285} \right]^3, \\
 n_n(r) &= 7.8103 \times 10^{-2} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{10.920} \right)^{3.079} \right]^3.
 \end{aligned} \tag{A2}$$

2. Slab-like nuclei - lasagna phase

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_p(r) &= 8.9660 \times 10^{-2} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{9.2401} \right)^{2.1320} \right]^3, \\
 n_n(r) &= 2.2281 \times 10^{-2} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{10.202} \right)^{2.2026} \right]^3.
 \end{aligned} \tag{A3}$$

3. Inside out nuclei

a. Cylindrical bubbles - antispaghetti phase

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_p(r) &= -4.2701 \times 10^{-3} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{12.91} \right)^{2.7140} \right]^3, \\
 n_n(r) &= -0.01508 \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{13.25} \right)^{2.294} \right]^3.
 \end{aligned} \tag{A4}$$

b. Spherical bubbles - antignocchi phase

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_p(r) &= -3.5618 \times 10^{-3} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{14.905} \right)^{2.3656} \right]^3, \\
 n_n(r) &= -1.2545 \times 10^{-2} \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{r}{15.295} \right)^{2.04} \right]^3.
 \end{aligned} \tag{A5}$$

Appendix B: Tables

TABLE I. Parameters of the Skyrme interaction. t_0 in MeV fm³, t_1, t_2 in MeV fm⁵; t_{3i} in MeV fm^{3+3 σ_i} . x_0, x_1, x_2, x_{3i} and σ_i dimensionless. For all parametrizations $t_4 = x_4 = 0$ and $t_5 = x_5 = 0$.

Skyrme	t_0	t_1	t_2	t_{31}	t_{32}	t_{33}	x_0	x_1	x_2	x_{31}	x_{32}	x_{33}	σ_1	σ_2	σ_3
GSKI	-1855.5	397.2	246.6	13858.0	-2694.1	-319.9	0.12	-1.76	-1.81	0.13	-1.19	-0.46	0.33	0.67	1.00

TABLE II. Parameters for nucleon distributions inside the Wigner-Seitz cell. n_b in fm⁻³. R_c, R_n, R_p, r_n, r_p in fm. t_n and t_p are dimensionless.

Shape	n_b	R_c	R_n	R_p	r_n	r_p	t_n	t_p
Spherical	0.030	22.317	11.667	9.3707	9.1036	7.6568	4.6250	6.2741
Rod-like	0.070	13.898	10.920	9.780	7.6374	6.9120	3.079	3.2285
Slab-like	0.080	11.115	10.202	9.2401	6.0853	5.4518	2.2026	2.1320
Cylindrical bubble	0.085	13.247	13.25	12.91	8.6599	8.7755	2.294	2.7140
Spherical bubble	0.086	15.316	15.295	14.905	10.349	10.359	2.04	2.3656

TABLE III. Parameters for nucleon distributions inside the Weigner-Seitz cell. n_j^i, n_j^o and n_j^{cent} in fm⁻³.

Shape	n_n^{cent}	n_n^i	n_n^o	n_p^{cent}	n_p^i	n_p^o
Spherical ($Y_p = 0.465$)	0.080121	2.8305×10^{-4}	0.030894	0.027774	0.023975	0
Rod-like	0.09525	1.0299×10^{-3}	0.05942	0.09525	8.8817	0
Slab-like	0.089660	1.2253×10^{-3}	0.067379	0.00673	5.4391×10^{-3}	0
Cylindrical bubble	0.07137	-8.7979×10^{-4}	0.08645	0	-3.1214×10^{-3}	4.2701×10^{-3}
Spherical bubble	0.072100	-5.3655×10^{-4}	0.08645	0	-2.012×10^{-3}	3.5618×10^{-3}